

Photometric Determination of Trace Amount of Nitrate in Soil and Plant Samples with Sulphosalicylic Acid

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Sulphosalicylic acid gives a better sensitivity for the determination of nitrate in comparison to phenol-disulphonic acid. The sensitivity of the present method is $0.012 \mu\text{g nitrate cm}^{-2}$. Beer's law is obeyed over the range 0.12 - 16.30 ppm with r.s.d. $\pm 0.12\%$. Tolerance limits, interferences and removal of different foreign ions have been studied. The method was employed for the analysis of nitrate in various soil and plant samples. The nitration product of sulphosalicylic acid has been isolated and characterised.

ONE of the most widely used methods for the spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of nitrate involves the nitration of aromatic compounds to form coloured products. Holler and Huch¹ studied the nitration of many xylenols and showed that 3,4-xyleneol was the best whereas Andrews² used 2,6-xyleneol. Harper³ determined nitrate by nitration of phenoldisulphonic acid. Vasil'eva⁴ reported that much better colouration may be attained by using sulphosalicylic acid in comparison to that obtained by using phenoldisulphonic acid. Thus, a higher sensitivity is expected by using this reagent.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were made in a Beckman 26 double beam uv-visible spectrophotometer equipped with matched quartz cells (1 cm). Systronics 331 expanded scale pH-meter equipped with a glass electrode was used for pH measurements. The ir spectrum was recorded on a Beckman infrared spectrophotometer.

A standard nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving 0.527 g of reagent grade potassium nitrate in double-distilled water and diluted to 1 l. Sulphosalicylic acid (E. Marck, Germany) was recrystallised from water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The reagent was used to prepare a $5.3 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution in double-distilled water. A buffer for pH 12 was made by mixing the solutions of 0.5M disodium hydrogen phosphate (0.5M) and sodium hydroxide (0.1M) in double-distilled water.

All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. All aqueous solutions were made using double-distilled water.

Procedure: Sulphosalicylic acid solution ($5.3 \times 10^{-3} M$, 2 ml), various volumes of standard nitrate solution ($5.2 \times 10^{-3} M$) and concentrated sulphuric

acid (sp. gr. 1.84, 0.1 ml) were taken in a small conical flask (with a funnel in its mouth) and was placed on a hot plate. The mixture was heated gently for 10 min. The mass was then cooled followed by the addition of sodium hydroxide solution (35%, 0.7 ml) and buffer solution (2 ml). The resulting mixture was diluted to 10 ml with double-distilled water. The absorbance of the final solution was measured at 410 nm using reagent blank as a reference.

Collection and treatment of soil samples: The soil samples used were collected from different areas throughout West Bengal. The samples were collected from the levels below the ground surface. At first the samples were dried in air and pulverised to a size to pass 8 mesh sieve. The samples were again dried in a desiccator. 10 gms of samples were taken in a 250 ml conical flask followed by 50 ml of a mixture of 3.0 mM sodium bicarbonate and 1.8 mM sodium carbonate as a leaching solution⁵. The flask was stoppered and shaken for 1 h in a mechanical shaker. The supernatant liquid was then decanted and centrifuged under 5000 r.p.m. An aliquot of 20 ml from the clear solution was made acidic with dilute sulphuric acid. The nitrite present was removed by urea⁶ (0.2 g), then the chloride present was removed by the following way using 1 ml 0.5% silver sulphate solution⁷. The precipitate of silver chloride was settled, filtered through a sintered glass crucible and finally washed with 1% sodium sulphate solution. The excess silver ion was removed by adding 0.2 g calcium hydroxide and 0.5 g magnesium carbonate⁸ and colour developed, if any, due to the presence of organic matter was decolorised by shaking with activated charcoal. The solution was filtered again through a sintered glass crucible and the precipitate was washed with the same washing solution. The volume of the resulting solution was then reduced to almost a dry mass and then treated with the reagent solution as described in the

standard procedure. The absorbance was measured after the solution was diluted suitably.

Collection and treatment of plant samples: Some samples of biofertilisers were dried in air and ground to pass 40 mesh screen. 0.1 g sample was taken in a 100 ml flask followed by the addition of 0.8-1.0 g powdered calcium sulphate to aid in filtering process⁵. 25 ml of silver sulphate solution (3.5 g l⁻¹) was added to it and shaken for 10-15 min. Excess silver ion was removed at pH 6.5 by adding 1 ml sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate (140 g l⁻¹ and adjusted to pH 6.5 with sodium hydroxide solution). The solid materials were removed by filtering through a sintered glass crucible and washed with 1% sodium sulphate solution. 2 ml calcium carbonate suspension (5 g l⁻¹) was added and the volume was reduced to 10 ml. 1 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide was mixed and the vessel covered with a watch glass was heated on a steam bath for 2 h to remove the organic matter, the residual peroxide removed by further heating. The mass was cooled and the reagent was treated as in the standard procedure. The absorbance value was recorded after suitable dilution of the resulting solution.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance values of several solutions containing different amounts of nitrate were measured against reagent blank in the range of 475-360 nm which showed a λ_{\max} at 410 nm. The molar absorptivity for the nitrated compound at this wave length is $4.86 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The effect of variation of pH was studied for the efficient colour development by base at final stage. The results indicated that pH 10.5 was suitable for the maximum colour development. But the colour intensity is not affected by higher pH values (e.g. 10.5-12.0).

To optimise the amount of reagent of the above procedure for a particular amount of nitrate (64.6 μg) various amounts of reagent were used. It was found that 1.5 ml, $5.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ sulphosalicylic acid was sufficient but higher amounts did not interfere.

Addition of different amounts of sulphuric acid to the fixed amounts of nitrate and reagent showed that maximum nitration was obtained by adding 0.1-0.2 ml concentrated sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84).

Beer's law and sensitivity: Beer's law was obeyed over the range 0.12-16.30 ppm. According to Sandell⁶ the optimum concentration range was 3.00-10.30 ppm. The corresponding Sandell sensitivity⁶ was 0.012 μg nitrate cm^{-2} . The relative standard deviation was found to be $\pm 0.12\%$. The confidence limit (95%) for 4 determinations was found to be 9.415 ± 0.323 ppm nitrate. The sensitivity and Beer's law range clearly indicate an improvement over the method using phenol disulphonic acid⁸.

Effect of added ions: For the study of the tolerance limits (within relative error $\pm 2\%$) of diverse ions, 64.6 μg nitrate was taken separately with varying concentration of other ions and the analyses were carried out by the recommended procedure. The tolerance limits in the determination of nitrate were as follows: 200 ppm of K^I, NH₄^I, Ca^{II}, Zn^{II}, acetate, urea, E.D.T.A.; 100 ppm of Cl⁻, PO₄³⁻, tartarate, SiO₃²⁻, S²⁻; 50 ppm of F⁻; and 10 ppm of Ag^I. On the other hand, interference due to Ni^{II} and Co^{II} were masked by E.D.T.A. upto 50 ppm. The interference by NO₂ was eliminated by urea⁶ and that of I⁻, Br⁻, SCN⁻ by silver sulphate⁷.

Nature of the compound: A small amount of the solid nitration product of sulphosalicylic acid as its sodium salt was isolated and compared with the compound obtained by the earlier reported method¹⁰. The result of the elemental analyses of the compound indicated nitro to reagent ratio as 1:1. The infrared spectrum of the isolated compound was studied in the solid phase using potassium bromide matrix. The result indicated the presence of NO₂ band at 1030 cm^{-1} . Moreover, the bands of C=O, C-O (phenol) of the reagent are present in the product.

Determination of nitrate in soil samples: Table 1 shows the results of the determination of nitrate in various soil samples of different places of West Bengal by the recommended procedure. The nitrate content of soil is subjected to change, particularly under conditions of warm moist storage. So, the determination should possibly be made sooner the sample is collected. The present reagent has been used for the routine analysis of soil sample with the precautions needed for soil containing appreciable amounts of chloride, nitrite and those giving extracts coloured with organic matter. The result shows that the sample collected from hilly area (Suka, Darjeeling) has lowest nitrate content. On the other hand, the nitrate content in industrial area (Hindmotor) is highest which may be due to the absorption of acid fumes in soil of the industrial areas. The results of nitrate levels in soil samples by the standard reduction method¹¹ are also given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—NITRATE CONTENT* OF SOIL EXTRACT

Location	Present method ppm	Standard reduction method ppm
Burdwan	10.6	9.5
Dubarajpur	9.6	9.0
Hindmotor	83.7	79.0
Khadra	8.8	10.0
Purulia	8.3	10.0
Shalun	10.5	9.1
Suka	6.7	6.0

* Average of three determinations.

Determination of nitrate in plant samples: As part of extensive study of fertiliser requirement of crops, nitrates in preference to other forms of

nitrogen are determined in plant materials. Table 2 shows the results of determination of nitrate in

Name of plant	In original plant extract ppm	After the addition* ppm	Recovery of added nitrate ppm	Percent recovery of added nitrate**
<i>Azollapinnata</i> R. Br., India	620	1130	510	102
<i>Azollapinnata</i> R. Br., Bangladesh	380	1100	520	104
<i>Azollapinnata</i> R. Br., Bangkok	1630	2110	480	96
<i>Azollapinnata</i> R. Br., Vietnam	3000	3510	510	102
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> Solms	660	1150	490	98
<i>Cirissa caromada</i> Linn. leaves	3650	4125	475	95

* 500 ppm of nitrate was added to each extract.
** Average of three determinations.

various plant samples which may be used for bio-fertiliser by the recommended procedure. These biofertiliser are under the genus of *azolla carissa*, and *eichhornia* which fix the atmospheric nitrogen symbiotically and convert into nitrate. In the case of plant samples the standard reduction method¹¹ was attempted. But after reduction of extracted nitrate to nitrite and addition of sulphanilamide, *N*-(1-naphthyl)-ethylenediamine hydrochloride a

colloidal matter appeared which could not be removed. Hence, the standard addition method was used for the plant samples to have the reproducibility of the method. In the plant sample analysis, 500 ppm nitrate was added to each of the plant extract and was estimated before and after the addition of nitrate by the present method. The percentage of recovery ranges from 95 to 104.

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